

OBTA, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW Our Mythical Childhood... Consolidator Grant Project

Our Mythical Hope in Children's and Young Adults' Culture... The (In)efficacy of Ancient Myths in Overcoming the Hardships of Life

OUR MYTHICAL HOPE IN EDUCATION WORKSHOPS EXPERIMENTAL SCHOOL PROJECT

We are pleased to continue our cooperation with two high schools – Mikołaj Rej in Warsaw and *Strumienie* in Józefów – that for the whole school year have worked within the research field chosen for this stage of the project, with the teachers adjusting it to their students' needs and interests. Now, during two workshops, we will have the opportunity to observe and discuss the results of this endeavour:

High School *Strumienie* in Józefów

- Short scenes from Shakespeare's *A Midsummer Night's Dream* in Latin,
- Mythological key to understanding the Polish national epic *Pan Tadeusz*,
- **Advertising posters** of students' design, showing today's reality through the prism of myths.

Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw

- **Students' dialogues** with mythical heroes,
- Echoes of myths in **Warsaw urban space**,
- Students' forms of **artistic expression**.

In focusing on the role of ancient myths in the life of young people, we are strengthening the bridge between the generations, including our Greek and Roman ancestors who raise us up to ever new endeavours – who give us hope for the future.

MAY THE CLASSICS BE WITH US!

Ubi et quando?

Monday, May 15, 2017, at 11.00 a.m., High School *Strumienie* in Józefów

Tuesday, May 16, 2017, at 10.00 a.m., Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, White Villa, Dobra 72

More information:

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